

Experience of Foreign Countries in Providing Employment of the Population

Fozilov Vahobjon Akrom o'g'li¹, **Uroqov Alimardon Sobir o'g'li**²

¹ Teacher, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, "Real Economy" department assistant trainee

² Student of the faculty of economics of the Samarkand institute of economics and service

Abstract:

In this article explores their experience in developed countries in the regulation of employment and the labor market. The experience of these countries provides opportunities to reduce unemployment in our country and increase the employment of the population with socially necessary labor.

Keywords: employment of the population, employment programs, employment models, foreign experience.

Introduction.

It is appropriate to use international experiences to improve the state employment regulation system. Regulation of the forms and methods of regulation of this field, using the world experience effectively, will help the development of villages. In the study of international experiences, it is appropriate to observe the activities of the International Labor Organization aimed at full employment, guarantee of employment, preservation and development of jobs. Leading employment policies of developed countries are based on the concept of labor market flexibility. It includes the regional and professional mobility of the labor force, indicators of flexibility of the labor force in terms of hiring, dismissal, inter-enterprise employee mobility, working time management. For example, in Sweden, the state plays a large role in the development of programs for the distribution and redistribution of national income based on taxes and public expenditures, and for maintaining the employment status (organization of collective work, creation of jobs, etc.). , in the USA, the influence of the government on the control of population employment has been reduced to a minimum level [1; p. 61]. In the world experience, the American, Swedish (Scandinavian), European, Japanese and Chinese models are distinguished among the models of

population employment. Of these, the American model has low production efficiency and small income for the majority of the working population. aimed at creating jobs.

Carrying out such a policy will keep unemployment at a low level and prevent financial and economic opposition from the government. The main directions of the modern employment policy of the USA are: increasing the quality of jobs in terms of increasing the salary level, ensuring professional growth in the future, maintaining jobs and increasing them. The US policy is primarily aimed at stimulating employment growth and increasing jobs, training and retraining workers, and supporting the hired workforce. The Swedish (Scandinavian) model is aimed at establishing average (satisfactory) working and income conditions in the public sector for all groups of the workforce. The disadvantage of this policy is the reduction and reduction of production and work without doubt Dependence on the financial means of the government, which leads to a sharp reduction of places.

The European model of employment policy is distinguished by its focus on reducing the number of jobs and increasing the income of the self-employed while increasing production efficiency. Such a policy requires the establishment of a costly system for a growing number of unemployed. The most negative aspect of this policy is long-term unemployment and many economic and financial obstacles related to it. In the Japanese model of population employment, the state studies not only urban, but also rural employment situations, and great attention is paid to providing the population with jobs. The system of employment aimed at the employment of employees until they reach the retirement age is widespread (especially in rural areas). Also, in Japan, the aim of long-term employment of employees, their professional training and qualification improvement is determined by the composition of jobs, the types of products produced. taking into account that the implementation at the level of the internal company, which presupposes the professional mobility of the employee within the company, creates an opportunity to educate employees in a positive attitude to work, to achieve a high level of work quality. The Chinese model of providing employment to the population is aimed at increasing the efficiency of the economy.

In developed countries, they are divided into the following groups according to the degree of strictness of the norms aimed at protecting employment: Countries with a liberal management model, according to which employers implement employee recruitment policies based on economic objectives (USA, Canada, Great Britain Britain, Ireland, Australia and New Zealand since the mid-1990s). Countries where labor relations are based on the preserved model, where employers face significant restrictions on the use of the required number of workers (Italy, Greece, Turkey, Germany and France) All other countries can be included in the middle group, because they have some area of legislation aimed at protecting employment, which exhibits severe restrictive measures, is in proportion to liberal legislation in other areas. The choice of forms and methods of employment regulation is related to a specific economic period. For example, the analysis of active and passive policies carried out abroad includes passive measures aimed at supporting the unemployed part of the population in countries with a peak of economic activity and constant growth, and entrepreneurship in a state of economic crisis. showed that attention is focused on the implementation of actions that create activity and direct it to active work, as well as ensuring employment. In the last decade, the government bodies of Japan and the USA are mostly large working with corporations. At this point, it should be mentioned that the determination of the amount of wages affects employment conditions.

In the countries of Western Europe, Africa and Asia, there is a lot of government intervention in the work of private companies. Examples of liberal indirect government management are the forms of government based on economic means in Germany and Great Britain. Non-profit organizations, such as the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, which provide the link between the state administration and the initiative of private enterprises, will have a great role in this.

Unemployment problems are almost non-existent in EU countries, although this indicator is measured by the share of GDP per capita, which is lower in rural areas than in urban areas in all EU countries. Only in some countries, the problems of employment in rural areas have been partially solved due to the fact that the main employment indicators of these countries are concentrated in rural areas. (For example, in Ireland, Spain, Greece and France, but excluding Finland, Italy and Portugal). Countries with high employment rates have tried to solve the problem of unemployment, even if it is in rural areas, by creating non-agricultural jobs. This development is caused by the large contribution of the country's GDP per capita and the acceleration of urbanization processes.

Regulation of foreign employment is carried out through the distribution and redistribution of foreign labor. For example, in industrialized countries facing a large influx of foreign labor (Germany, France, etc.), a number of programs aimed at sending foreign workers back to their countries have been developed in recent years. In some European countries, it is possible to use the experience of regulating employment in rural areas in regions with a high level of urbanization. Hired labor is used in many enterprises of developed countries. As a basis for this, the legal basis of this type of work was formed in 1980-1990. Conventions No. 181 and No. 188 on private personnel agencies were adopted at the 85th session of the ILO in 1997. The highest indicator of the use of hired labor belongs to the United States. The share of employees of this category in the country was 4.5% of the total employed population.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Studying and analyzing the experience of the practices used in foreign countries on the socio-economic mechanisms of increasing the employment of the population in the conditions of deepening the current economic reforms is one of the aspects of the experience of these countries that are suitable for our country. using it, it allows to identify and put into practice the important, new promising directions of increasing the employment level of the population. In the context of deepening economic reforms, scientific research and analysis of the experience of foreign practices on the socio-economic mechanisms of increasing the employment of the population, using the advanced aspects of the experience of these countries, which are convenient for our republic, is an effective, promising way to increase the level of employment of the population. allows to determine the directions and apply them in practice

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